

THE ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT IN ENHANCING LEARNERS' DEVELOPMENT IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

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The Role of Educational Management in Enhancing Learners' Development in Public Elementary Schools

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Abstract

This study used quantitative research design to investigate how the management of learning improved on the development of students of public elementary schools based on 50 respondents of the head teachers from the 2nd Congressional District of Masbate Province, Aroroy, Baleno, Mobo, Milagros, Mandaon, and Balud. Surveys through online questionnaires are collected and interpreted by employing weighted mean, frequency, percentage, and rank of analysis. The study findings show that for school success, communication has to be transparent to ensure trust and improve problem-solving ability. It creates a positive school culture. Effective communication between teachers and administrators improves academic performance. As far as the impact of educational management on holistic learner development is concerned, findings showed that a supportive and meaningful learning environment positively influences enjoyment, engagement, teaching, and learning. This also helps improve academic performance. Further, consistent leadership practices are important for the stability and safety of students so that they can focus on learning. Consistency also gives a sense of security as well as fairness and trust. Results of the study led to the conclusion that only transparent communication, a positive learning environment, and consistent leadership would establish trust, engagement, and academic success. Recommendations included practicing transparent communication among school heads and teachers, creating a safe and stimulating environment based on mutual respect, and showing consistency in order to ensure trust and positive outcomes related to learning. These practices are vital for aligning educational management strategies with the goal of enhancing learners' overall development.

Keywords: *educational management, public elementary schools, management style*

Introduction

Educational management is the administration of the educational system with the assistance of professionals and material resources. Its goal is to supervise, plan, strategize, and implement structures in order to carry out an education system. It should be noted that educational management is not limited to schools; rather, it encompasses all types of institutions, including higher education institutes, public schools, and private schools.

The primary functions and administration of educational management are to develop education policies, conduct research, or consult to help evaluate and develop ways to enrich and enhance the educational system at an institutional level. It also entails improving both teaching and learning in a school environment through the effective use of administrative tools, education software, and best practices.

Thus, it plays a crucial role in enhancing learners' development in public elementary schools by: Establishing clear expectations and routines, providing specific feedback, and creating opportunities for students to respond, fostering a positive school learning climate and providing instructional guidance. Engaging with families and communities to support student learning, Implementing School-Based Management (SBM) to tailor education to local needs.

These strategies are supported by research and are essential for student academic and social success. According to Cezmi and Toprak (2014), leadership and management is a concept that is known as an effort that directs organizational activities to achieve a common goal. With the ever-changing educational landscape, school heads must incorporate a wide range of leadership and management skills and styles in order to direct their school organization toward that common goal and a well-directed vision. Leadership style employed by the school administrator is complex and plays an integral role in developing the culture in a school (Smith, 2016). It refers to the special behavior of the leaders for motivating a group of employees for realization of a part of the organizational goal. Management style, however, refers to the philosophical mechanism and ability of the managers to influence or affect a group in line with securing the goal (Vahedi and Asadi, 2013).

Leadership and management need to be given equal prominence if schools are to operate effectively and achieve their objectives. Leading and managing are distinct, but both are important. The challenge of modern organizations requires the objective perspective of the manager as well as the ashes of vision and commitment wise leadership provides (Bolman & Deal, 1997, p. xiii-xiv).

In the Philippines, the principal is expected to be both an instructional leader and administrative manager. The school head, who may be assisted by assistant school head, shall be both an instructional leader and an administrative manager. He/she is a person responsible for administrative and instructional supervision of the school or cluster of schools. This specifies the responsibilities of principals as instructional leaders and administrative managers: creating an environment within the school that is conducive to teaching and learning;

implementing the school curriculum and being accountable for higher learning outcomes; introducing new and innovative models of instruction to achieve higher learning outcomes; and encouraging staff development (Republic Act 9155, 2001). As distinct from other parts of the Philippines, the educational challenges in the Masbate Province are unique to the Bicol Region. These public elementary schools in the SDO Masbate Province Division-the three districts that include Mandaon North and South, Baleno, and Milagros West-face major resource constraints that are compounded by geographical isolation, socio-economic issues which impact learner development and performance.

These issues illustrate the imperative importance of examining how educational management enhances learners' growth. The aim of this study will be to assess the impact of educational management practices on the academic and holistic development of learners in these districts. This research seeks to identify actionable strategies that school leaders can utilize to align local contexts with successful management practices that promote learner success. This study aims to analyze the role of educational management in enhancing learners' development in public elementary schools.

Research Questions

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What specific aspects of educational management most significantly impact the academic achievement of elementary learners?
2. In what ways does educational management influence the overall development of the learners?
3. What strategies can school leaders implement to align educational management practices with the goal of enhancing overall learner development?

Methodology

The quantitative research design was utilized to gather and systematically analyze data for this study. Google Form was utilized to disseminate a questionnaire checklist to the respondents to facilitate easy access and prompt completion with 50 school heads, randomly selected participants from the districts of SDO Masbate Province Division under the 2nd Congressional District. These districts included Mandaon North and South, Milagros West, and Baleno District.

The questionnaire was divided into three parts: The aspects of educational management that most significantly impact the academic achievement of elementary learners; the ways in which educational management influences the overall development of the learners; and strategies that school leaders can implement to align educational management practices with the goal of enhancing overall learner development. Since the respondents involved were school heads actively engaged in fulfilling their responsibility, the researchers allowed them adequate time to accomplish the survey, provide authentic responses, and allow themselves to provide thoughtful responses. Follow-up reminders were sent so that the accomplished questionnaires can be submitted accordingly.

The responses were collected and data carefully compiled, evaluated, and interpreted to establish meaningful conclusions. The average weighted mean was utilized in the assessment of those factors of educational management that have a great influence on the academic achievement of elementary learners and how school leaders can make strategies to promote learner development. Ranking was utilized in evaluating the influence of educational management on the overall development of learners.

Results and Discussion

This presents the findings from the study titled "Role of Educational Management in Enhancing Learners' Development in Public Elementary Schools." The study focused on the specific aspects of educational management most significantly impact the academic achievement of elementary learners, how educational management influence the overall development of the learners, and the strategies of school leaders in aligning educational management practices with the goal of enhancing overall development of learners.

Table 1. *Specific Aspects of Educational management most significantly impact the academic achievement of elementary learners*

<i>Specific Aspects of Educational Management</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Strategic Planning and Goal Setting.	4.68	Strongly Agree
Optimal Resource Management.	4.52	Strongly Agree
Transparent Communication.	4.72	Strongly Agree
Continues Professional Development.	3.88	Agree
Adaptive Decision Making.	4.36	Strongly Agree
Clear Vision and Mission.	4.7	Strongly Agree

Table 1 shows specific aspects of educational management most significantly impact the academic achievement of elementary learners. It includes weighted mean and interpretation.

As shown in the table, the specific aspects of educational management most significantly impact the academic achievement of elementary learners were computed according to weighted mean and its interpretation. "Transparent Communication" had a weighted mean of 4.73 interpreted as "Strongly agree" which has the highest weighted mean among the specific aspects of educational management, and "Continuous Professional Development" had a weighted mean 3.88 interpreted as "Agree" which has the lowest

weighted mean.

Transparency in communication can have a profound impact on an organization. A case in point is a charity I led for a number of years. In 2014 they faced financial difficulties after losing a significant grant. The charity also suffered a much smaller (less than 10% of the grant) fraud incident. The leadership took the bold step of being open about both issues, despite the risk to their reputation. The result? Supporters appreciated the honesty and contributed generously to an appeal, helping the charity raise the required funds in record time.

In present time, all professionals need to continuously involve in their PD to keep abreast with the latest in the field and have a competitive edge over others. Likewise, PD of teachers has also become significant for those who are concerned about their own learning and development, and for those who are seeking improvement in students' achievement (Patton, Parker & Tannehill 2015; Bredeson & Johansson, 2000). Moreover, with the passage of time, even societies have recognized the importance of teachers as one of the key variable that needs transformation in order to improve the education system but as one of the important change agent to facilitate and produce better future leaders (Elmore, 2004; Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012). This changed part of teachers by being the subject and object of change has resulted in making their professional development a challenging area receiving much thought, awareness and consideration in the recent decades (Darling-Hammond & McLaughlin, 2011; Patton et al., 2015)

The finding explicitly implied that transparent communication is essential for the success of any school. By promoting open and honest communication between teachers and administrators, schools can build trust, improve problem-solving and create a positive school culture.

Table 2. Ways on How Educational Management influence the overall development of the learners

<i>Ways on How Educational management influence the overall development of the learners.</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Provide a variety of differentiated instruction method.	49	94.2	1
Create a flexible seating arrangement.	24	46.2	7
Allow for different communication styles.	34	65.4	4
Encourage students' collaboration.	49	94.2	1
Use positive reinforcement.	46	88.5	2
Modify assignments as needed.	25	48.1	6
Create a positive classroom environment.	49	94.2	1
Use cooperative learning.	44	84.6	3
Use task simplification.	32	61.5	5

Table 2 shows the ways educational management influence the overall development of the learners. The results were computed using frequency, percentage and rank. Rank 1 were "Create a positive classroom environment", "Encourage students' collaboration" and "Provide a variety of differentiated instruction method" had a frequency of 49 or 94.2 percent.

Reinforcement is a response used to guide student behavior towards a desired outcome. In Freeman's (2015) research, positive reinforcement was seen to be more effective than negative reinforcement when it came time to promote compliant behavior. She had the opportunity of studying the effects that lead to student drop outs. While doing so, she came to find that the absence of a positive student - teacher relationship was a missing factor that led students to drop out (Freeman, 2015). Research conducted by Morin (2016) also finds that positive reinforcement provides students with the support needed to reach the desired behaviors. She conducted interviews and observations to analyze the effects of both inclusion and positive reinforcement in classroom environments. Through that research she found that verbal reinforcement acted as the most influential behavior led by teachers and accepted by students (Morin, 2016).

One of the benefits of practicing collaboration is the ability to break down walls and silos created within institutions, through formal and informal processes. One of the walls created is between administrators, faculty, and students. There is an expectation that student affairs professionals will interact with students. This same expectation is not always present for administrators and faculty. This is not the culture at NSU. Faculty and administrators practice accessibility to and involvement with students in the same manner traditionally found in student affairs. This increased accessibility ultimately adds to a campus environment that fosters student success. According to a staff member speaking to the accessibility of academic administration: "So these are the kind of people when the students see them, wow, the Dean is here, the President is here, the provost is here. If I have problems I can actually talk directly to these individuals." In order to maintain a culture of collaboration, staff may believe that they have easy access to individuals that normally are shielded by bureaucracy. Faculty also desired to be highly accessible to students, using technology to increase their ability to help students experiencing challenges with their work. The faculty encourage students to use their cell phones in courses to answer and ask questions via Twitter and text messages. This is possible due to the campus being connected via Energy Wireless.

To differentiate instruction is to acknowledge various student backgrounds, readiness levels, languages, interests and learning profiles (Hall, 2002). Differentiated instruction sees the learning experience as social and collaborative, the responsibility of what happens in the classroom is first to the teacher, but also to the learner (Tomlinson, 2004c). Building on this definition, Mulroy and Eddinger (2003) add that differentiated instruction emerged within the context of increasingly diverse student populations. Within the learning environment permitted by the differentiated instruction model, teachers, support staff and professionals collaborate to create an optimal learning experience for students (Mulroy and Eddinger, 2003). Also in this environment, each student is valued for his or her unique

strengths, while being offered opportunities to demonstrate skills through a variety of assessment techniques (Mulroy and Eddinger, 2003; Tomlinson, 2001a; Tomlinson and Kalbfleisch, 1998; Tuttle, 2000).

The finding explicitly implied that a positive and purposeful learning environment can boost enjoyment and engagement. It can also help to enrich teaching and learning and improve academic performance. Therefore, it is essential that school strive to ensure that they are providing their students with the best possible learning environment.

Table 3. *Strategies of School Leaders to Align Educational Management Practices with the Goal of Enhancing Overall Learner Development*

<i>Strategies of School Leaders to Align Educational Management Practices with the Goal of Enhancing Overall Learner Development</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Establish and maintain relationships	4.62	Strongly Agree
Establishing morning routines	4.26	Strongly Agree
Strategic Classroom seating	4.28	Strongly Agree
Implementation positive behavior intervention strategies	4.7	Strongly Agree
Setting clear expectations	4.68	Strongly Agree
Be consistent in applying rules	4.74	Strongly Agree

Table 3 shows the strategies can school leaders implement to align educational management practices with the goal of enhancing overall learner development. It includes weighted mean, interpretation and rank. As shown in the table, the strategies can school leaders implement to align educational management practices with the goal of enhancing overall learner development were computed according to weighted mean and its interpretation. “Be consistent in applying rules” had a weighted mean of 4.74 interpreted as “Strongly agree” which has the highest weighted mean among the strategies and “implementation positive behavior intervention strategies” had a weighted mean of 4.7 interpreted as “Strongly agree” which has the lowest weighted mean.

One of the classroom management strategies that teachers can use to develop student discipline is through the consistent application of rules and procedures. In line with Susanto (2018, p. 120), which states that in the school context, class conditions can be framed in the form of rules and procedures, when students obey them, it means students can be declared disciplined. But on the contrary, when students do not comply, students are declared undisciplined. Therefore, the teacher as one of the school parties who can facilitate students in forming discipline, must apply rules and procedures consistently. This is in line with Kharisma & Suyatno (2019, p. 137), that consistent application of rules and procedures can form discipline in students. Application of rules and procedures this is very important namely in order to achieve learning objectives, learning can be effective and conducive, and students can be equipped to have a disciplined attitude.

Managing student behaviors is very difficult to begin with, but the idea of management in a safe and positive way lessens the negative impact in the classroom. Positive Reinforcement allows students to be addressed in a positive manner and redirected in a way that encourages and praises their behavior (Conley, 2014). Skinner believed in positive reinforcement as he established positive reinforcement as a more effective way of producing change than punishment. Through his research, not only did he define the different between positive and negative reinforcement, but he also found that negative reinforcement leads to escape and active avoidance (Frisoli, 2018). He assessed students on their lack clarity, fear of failure, time and complication of tasks, lack of directions, and lack of positive reinforcement as he believed they were the five primary obstacles of learning for children in a classroom (Frisoli, 2018).

The finding explicitly implied that when leaders are consistent, students quickly learn what to expect. Since this allow them to feel safe, they are able to focus their energy on learning. It can give out a message of fairness and positivity so, that children know where they stand, and this allow them to trust and be trusted.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Transparent communication is essential for the success of any school. By promoting open and honest communication between teachers and administrators, schools can build trust, improve problem-solving and create a positive school culture.

A positive and purposeful learning environment can boost enjoyment and engagement. It can also help to enrich teaching and learning and improve academic performance. Therefore, it is essential that school strive to ensure that they are providing their students with the best possible learning environment.

When leaders are consistent, students quickly learn what to expect. Since this allow them to feel safe, they are able to focus their energy on learning. It can give out a message of fairness and positivity so, that children know where they stand, and this allow them to trust and be trusted.

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were drawn:

Establish routine feedback mechanisms-survey or suggestion box-to ensure open communication between teachers and administrators, based on mutual trust and collaboration.

Conduct regular assessments of the school's physical and psychological learning environment and initiate initiatives that could improve aspects requiring attention, supportive of student engagement and academic success.

Formulate explicit and consistent school policies and practices which promote equity and accountability in order to facilitate student learning in the classroom environment

References

- Affholder, L. P. (2003). Differentiated instruction in inclusive elementary classrooms. Unpublished EdD thesis. University of Kansas, Kansas.
- Bender, Y. (2005). *The tactful teacher: Effective communication with parents, colleagues, and administrators*. Nomad Press. Brown, B. (2018). *Dare to lead: Brave work, tough conversations, whole hearts*. Random House
- Bolam, R. 1999. Educational administration, leadership and management: toward a research agenda. In *Educational Management: Redefining Theory and policy*.
- Bush, T. (1999). *Theories of Educational Management*.
- Bjork, C. (2013). "Teacher training, school norms and teacher effectiveness in Indonesia," in *Education in Indonesia*, eds D. Suryadarma and G. W. Jones (Pasir Panjang: Institute of Southeast Asian Studies (ISEAS) Publishing), 53–67. doi: 10.1355/9789814459877-008
- Cherry, K. (2018). Positive Reinforcement can be used to teach new behaviors. VeryWellMind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-positive-reinforcement-2795412>
- Conley, Anmarie G. (2014). Positive Reinforcement Behavior Plans and the Effects on Student Behavior. *Education and Human Development Master's Theses*. 346. https://digitalcommons.brockport.edu/ehd_theses/346
- Darling-Hammond, L., & McLaughlin, M. W. (1995). Policies that support professional development in an era of reform. *Phi delta kappan*, 76(8), 597-604.
- Desimone, L. M., Porter, A. C., Garet, M. S., Yoon, K. S., & Birman, B. F. (2002). Effects of professional development on teachers' instruction: Results from a three-year longitudinal study. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 24, 81-112.
- Kezar, A. J. (2006). Redesigning for collaboration in learning initiatives: an examination of four highly collaborative campuses. *J. High. Educ.* 77, 804–838. doi: 10.1353/jhe.2006.0043
- Kimani, G. N. (n.d.). *Educational Management*. African Virtual University.
- Topley, M. The art of leadership communication: Transparency, listening, and effective feedback. *BDJ In Pract* 36, 22–23 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41404-023-2181-9>

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